

A Simple Camera CMOS Sensor Noise Model

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Abstract: There are different sources of information, like on the Internet, depicting the behavior and noise characterization in a raw image from a digital CMOS sensor. In those posts, it is said the shot noise and the PRNU noise are additive components of the raw image variance, where —with respect to the signal— the first one has a linear relationship, while the second has a quadratic one. However, there is not an explanation about how this behavior arises. This paper fills that gap, proposing a simple model based on known CMOS sensor characteristics and shows how this model explains the aforementioned noise profile.

1 Introduction

There is interesting information, like in in the web, depicting the behavior and noise characterization of a digital SLR camera with a CMOS sensor, like in this interesting [Mar14] article. In posts like these, it is said the *Shot Noise* and the *PRNU noise* are additive components of the raw image variance, where with respect to the signal; the first one has a linear relationship while the second one has a quadratic relationship. However, there is not an explanation about how this behavior arises, even when the presented data clearly supports those affirmations.

With the desire of getting a mathematical model explaining why the aforementioned noise components have that given mathematical profile we have used some properties of the statistical *variance* and *expected value* on a simple sensor model and we propose a simple mathematical sensor model and the equations derived from that model explaining the aforementioned noise profile.

In this article we will develop that sensor model from the scratch. But we will give just simple definitions for the intervening elements. Here we will focus on the interplay between those elements from a rather a theoretical point of view but also by using real data. We will use the formulas and notation given in [Dela14].

2 The Image Noise

The image noise is random spikes of luminance change —in each of the RGB image channels— in places where it is expected to be uniform or changing gradually. It is more noticeable in the dark areas and when the image is enlarged or closely inspected at pixel level. The noise can be described as composed by "*luminance noise*" and "*color noise*", where "*luminance noise*" is noise keeping basically the same overall hue whilst in "*color noise*" (also called "*chroma noise*") there is also changes in the hue. However, as the noise is random changes in the RGB channels, its presence in a raw image always involves both noise types. Please see the following sample.

Figure 1. The image right side contains color and luminance noise. The left side contains only luminance noise. The image is enlarged at 150%.

Besides creative or aesthetic intentions, the *color noise* is almost always undesirable. However, the *luminance noise* is not necessarily an unwanted image feature; sometimes it is required to avoid a posterized or plasticized look.

As the noise is luminance change, it is best measured with the *Standard Deviation* statistic. From now to on, when referring to the noise amount, we will be talking about the *Standard Deviation* (σ) of the luminosity along the image surface.

The human vision can resolve a change of luminosity at and above about 1% [Poy14]. Setting aside the value, this way to detect luminosity changes, on the base of a contrast ratio, means that the same noise is more noticeable when the average luminosity is lower and is less noticeable —or not noticeable at all— when the average luminosity is higher. In turn, this implies that the best way to measure the visual impact of the noise is considering the proportion between the *Noise* and the *average luminosity* of the image area containing the noise. The "classic" way to express this proportion is through the *Signal to Noise* ratio (usually abbreviated as *S/N* or *SNR*); this is the (arithmetic) mean or average luminosity divided by the amount of noise (*Standard Deviation*).

In this paper we will talk about the *average luminosity* and its *Standard Deviation* as measured from the pixels values in a raw image: linear values. In such case, it is said the pixel value has ADU (Analog-to-Digital Unit) as measurement unit.

It is implicit that the *Mean* and *Standard Deviation* are calculated among the pixels of the same image, over an area where all the pixels are expected to have the same luminosity: the photo target is a plain uniformly lit surface.

$$SNR = \text{Mean_pixel_Luminosity} / \text{StdDev_pixel_Luminosity} = \text{Mean}/\text{Noise} \quad \text{Eq. 2.1}$$

In the practice we will approximate the luminosity *expected value* (denoted with the *Eva()* operator) with the image sample *mean luminosity*, and the *standard deviation* will be obtained from the image sample variance (denoted with the *Var()* operator).

In the following equations ADU represents the reading from each photosite in the camera sensor recorded in each raw image pixel.

$$SNR = \frac{Mean}{Noise} = \frac{Eva(ADU)}{StdDev(ADU)} = \frac{Eva(ADU)}{\sqrt{Var(ADU)}} \quad \text{Eq. 2.2}$$

As the *Signal to Noise* ratio can have a very broad range of values, it is normally expressed by its logarithm. This is can be a base 2 logarithm, in which case it is said the SNR is expressed in stops.

$$SNR_Stops = \log_2(SNR) = \log_2\left(\frac{Mean}{Noise}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 2.3}$$

The SNR ratio is sometimes also expressed in decibels (dB), in which case it is calculated as 20 times the base 10 logarithm of the SNR.

$$SNR_dB = 20 \cdot \log_{10}(SNR) = \log_{10}\left(\frac{Mean}{Noise}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 2.4}$$

In the following table we have SNR categories that, according to ISO 12232:2006 standard and DxO Mark [Dxonc], can be considered as a reference for good, poor and bad noise levels. They are expressed in the three forms: the SNR ratio itself, in stops and in dB. The borders between neighbor categories are blurry and seem to overlap because where one ends the other begins.

Noise Category	Ratio	Stops	dB
Good when above to	80	6.3	38
Acceptable when above to	40	5.32	32
Non acceptable from and above to	10	3.32	20
Very bad when below of	10	3.32	20

A change of 6 dB approximately corresponds to a factor of 2 over the SNR. For example, notice in the table above, how when the SNR in dB changes from 38 to 32 (6 dB) the SNR changes from 80 to 40, effectively corresponding to a factor of two.

3 A Simple DSLR Camera Sensor Math Model

Each sensor photosite is sensitive —mainly— to only one of the RGB (red, green and blue) color components that will compose the final image after the image raw data processing. The following picture describes in simple but a meaningful way how the DSLR sensor converts the light hitting it to RGB pixel values in ADUs.

Figure 3.1. Photosites processing the light hitting it.

The light hitting the sensor during the exposition time can be described as comprised by photons. When each photon reaches a particular layer on the sensor silicon, the photon produces an electron. The unit for a quantity of electrons is "e⁻".

Once the exposition time has ended, the ADC (*Analog to Digital Converter* or *A/D Converter*) in the sensor circuitry, "counts" how many electrons are in each photosite and converts that count to ADUs. In this quantization, we will say, the ADC uses a conversion factor "M" (from **M**ultiplier), with the unit "ADU/e⁻", to *multiply* the tally of electrons and get the corresponding ADU value. Before the exposition time begins, all the photosites are *reset* in order to start the exposition with their electron count set to zero.

The "M" rate depends only on the ISO speed setting of the camera. For higher ISO values, "M" is higher, requiring fewer electrons to make an ADU, resulting in a more light-sensitive sensor as expected.

The flux of the photons hitting each photosite is proportional to the intensity of the light originating the photons. This way—as expected—the darker areas of the photographed scene will correspond to a low count of electrons and in consequence low ADU values, whilst the brighter areas will correspond to higher ADU values. We will represent the count of electrons in each photosite—at the end of the exposition time—with the symbol "EL" (for **E**lectrons) and using the unit "e⁻".

So far, our model prototype for the sensor is:

$$ADU = M \cdot EL \tag{Eq. 3.1}$$

3.1 Photon Shot Noise

Up to this point of our model (Eq 3.1), at first glance it seems we still don't have a source of noise, but we already have it, and it is the count of electrons represented by "EL".

Even with a perfectly uniform illumination on the photo target, the count of electrons in each photosite after the exposition time is not the same. That count, instead of a common value

among the photosites, is a random variable; those different values on the image surface are the kind of noise called *Photon Shot Noise*.

To understand this, let's imagine a large set of identical mugs set under a uniform rain, where at the end of the rain no mug was overflowed.

Figure 2.2. Rain as a Poisson Process.

If after the rain, we check the mugs, we will find that the amount of rain collected in each one is not very different from the others. But if we measure it very precisely, we will find different amounts of rain in each mug. Something similar occurs with the photons hitting the photosites. This is not a formal explanation, but it gives an idea of what is going on.

A more formal explanation is that even if the flux of photons is constant and uniformly over the sensor photosites, the amount of photons that hit each photosite is not a constant but a random variable following a *Poisson distribution* because the arriving of those photons follows a *Poisson process*.

A *Poisson process* can be described [WIKpp] as "a given number of discrete events occurring in a fixed interval of time and/or space, where these events occur with a known average rate and independently of the time since the last event". In our case, the discrete event is the photon hitting the photosite, and "in a fixed time and space" corresponds to the exposition time over each photosite surface, at a rate which effectively is independent of any previously arrived photon.

It is customary to represent the Poisson distribution *mean* and *variance* them with the Greek letter lambda " λ ", as we will do in the following equations: " λ " will represent the *expected value* and the *variance* of the electron count in each photosite.

Applying the *expected value* to both equation sides of our model prototype equation (Eq. 3.1), we get:

$$Eva(ADU) = Eva(M \cdot \mathbf{EL})$$

$$Eva(ADU) = M \cdot \lambda \tag{Eq. 3.2}$$

When we evaluate the *variance* to both equation sides of our model prototype we get:

$$Var(ADU) = Var(M \cdot \mathbf{EL}) \tag{Eq. 3.3}$$

$$\text{Var}(ADU) = M^2 \cdot \lambda$$

Now we can see the pixel *expected value* and its *variance* are linearly related:

$$\text{Var}(ADU) = M \cdot \text{Eva}(ADU) \tag{Eq. 3.4}$$

The last equation tells us that under the assumption the noise has a *Poisson distribution*; the image luminosity *variance* will have a linear relationship with its *expected value*.

Notice that these last equations, derived from our model *prototype*, are all of them over-simplifications of the sensor noise model, disregarding other sources of noise that we will include later. Despite of that, they will be useful to show the *photon noise* as a fact has a *Poisson distribution*, just because that source of noise is the main noise component in most DSLR sensor cameras. We will develop more fitted equations later on.

We can get a hint about the validity of the affirmation "*the electrons are produced following the Poisson distribution*" through the following experiment: We have taken 34 shots, in identical conditions (from a burst of consecutive shots), to the same chart, with the focus slightly blurred to avoid to capture noise from the structure of the surface of our target chart. One of those shots is shown in the following figure.

Figure 3.3. Test shot of the chart.

The chart contains 35 patches at different levels of luminance. As we saw in Eq. 3.4, we can predict the expected pixel value in the chart patches will have a linear relationship with their variance.

Figure 3.4. Plot of the green photosites values: pixel values variance versus average.

As estimators of the *variance* and *expected value* we will use the sample *average* and *variance* from a 60 pixels square inside each patch in each of the 34 raw image files from shots to the chart shown in Figure 3.3. For the sake of brevity we will analyze only the readings from the green sensitive photosites.

In the figure 3.4, we plot each sample *variance* (vertical axis) against its *Average* (horizontal axis), where the data from the same patch in the chart has the same color code. We can see there how they really have a linear relationship. Unfortunately, the data is heteroscedastic, and we cannot just use OLS to linearly correlate the *variance* with the *Average*, instead we must use a weighted robust regression, with the reciprocal value of the squared averages as weights to solve the heteroscedasticity issue. Considering this, the dotted line trend shown in the plot, correlating the *variance* with the *average*, has a *Coefficient of Determination* (R^2) of 97.8% with p-values for both linear parameters (intercept and slope) below to $2.2E-16$, as indicators that the linear model for the data is very significant, which in turn allows to say the *Photon Noise* has a *Poisson Distribution* with a chance very close to zero of being wrong.

The equations 3.1 and 3.4 depicts a “perfect” or “ideal” camera sensor, where the only source of noise is the *photon shot noise*, caused not by imperfections in the sensor but because the own nature of the light. A camera sensor noise can be assessed with respect to this limit knowing its noise cannot be lower than this.

$$PhotonNoise = \sqrt{M \cdot Eva(ADU)} \quad \text{Eq. 3.5}$$

$$SNR_{PhotoNoise} = \sqrt{\frac{Eva(ADU)}{M}} \quad \text{Eq. 3.6}$$

When the above equations are represented in a log-log plot, the photon shot noise and SNR of that type of noise corresponds to a line with slope of $\frac{1}{2}$.

3.2 Read Noise

The following equation shows our sensor model as is at this stage of development. As the "EL" term, representing the amount of electrons collected by the photosite, is a random variable, we will show it using bold typeface.

$$ADU = M \cdot \mathbf{EL} \quad \text{Eq. 3.7}$$

In APS (from **A**ctive **P**ixel **S**ensor) sensors, each photosite is connected to the electronic circuitry responsible for converting the charge from the electrons —produced by the photon shots— to voltage, and conduct it as input to the *A/D Converter*. As this processing line is not perfect, the output of the *A/D Converter* is not exactly proportional to the amount of electrons from the photon shots. There is always a bias or base level of ADUs coming out from the *A/D Converter*, even when there are not electrons at all in the photosites, as in a photograph taken with the lens cap on. This noise is called *Read Noise*.

The following sequence of images tries to explain how the *Read Noise* bias can be clipped from the ADU values, but even though the *Read Noise* stays in the image.

Figure 4.5. “Simulation” showing how the signal (2) gets mixed with the *read noise* (1), and how even after the *read noise* bias is removed (3 to 4) the resulting signal (4) still contains the *read noise* (3).

In the images of figure 3.5:

1. **The sensor Read Noise.** It is like "a fake signal" around an average of 500 ADU (in this

example). The intensity of the noise in these graphs is represented by the height of the emerald band.

2. **The signal collected in the photosites.** Even when the source is uniformly lit with an *expected value* of 300 ADU, the signal (red line) is not flat because it contains the *Photon Noise*.
3. **The output of the A/D Converter**, represented by the red thick line, contains the signal biased by the *Read Noise*. This signal contains more noise than the “real” signal (in image 2), because it also contains the *Read Noise*.
4. **The *Read Noise* “correction”.** The *Read Noise* bias is subtracted from the ADU values. If the result of this subtraction is a negative value, the pixel is set to zero. Now the red signal has an average of 300 ADUs as expected, but the additional noise that came from the *Read Noise* is still there: the height of the emerald band is the same as in the step 3. This *Read Noise* correction, in some camera brands (e.g. Nikon) is made in-camera or otherwise by raw image processing software.

We will add the *Read Noise* to our model using the term "**RNS**", representing the *Read Noise* signal bias in each photosite ADU reading. It is in bold typeface because it is a random variable; it varies from photosite to photosite. The term $-\mu_{RNS}$ corresponds to the **Read Noise** “correction” where the average RNS bias is subtracted from the ADU values as in the step (4) in the Figure 3.5.

$$ADU = M \cdot \mathbf{EL} + \mathbf{RNS} - \mu_{RNS} \quad \text{Eq. 3.8}$$

To simplify our formulas, the term "RN" will represent the *Read Noise*, so "RN²" will represent its *variance*. Furthermore

$$Var(RNS) = RN^2 \quad \text{Eq. 3.9}$$

$$StdDev(RNS) = RN \quad \text{Eq. 3.10}$$

We must realize that the *Read noise* “correction” removes the RNS bias in the photosites values, but even though, the RNS *noise* stays in the image: If we take the *expected value* to the Eq. 3.8, we can see how the RNS bias is removed, but when we take their *variance*, the read noise (RN) is still in the image.

$$Eva(ADU_{RNC}) = M \cdot \lambda + Eva(\mathbf{RNS}) - \mu_{RNS}$$

$$Eva(ADU_{RNC}) = M \cdot \lambda + \mu_{RNS} - \mu_{RNS}$$

$$Eva(ADU_{RNC}) = M \cdot \lambda \quad \text{Eq. 3.11}$$

$$Var(ADU) = Var(M \cdot \mathbf{EL}) + Var(\mathbf{RNS}) + Var(\mu_{RNS})$$

$$Var(ADU) = M^2 \cdot \lambda + RN^2 \quad \text{Eq. 3.12}$$

It must be clear the *Read Noise* is completely independent of the *Photon Noise*. The *Read Noise* is related to imperfections in the sensor electronic and is independent of the intensity of the light hitting the sensor. On the contrary, the *Photon Noise* is caused by the physical nature of the light and related to its intensity but is totally unrelated to the sensor processing. That independence is implicit in Eq. 3.12; it doesn't include the *covariance* between **EL** and **RNS**

because it is zero.

3.3 PRNU Noise

All the photosites are not made equal—even those filtering the light for the same color—are not perfectly equally sensitive to the light. The micro-lenses over each photosite, the layer collecting the produced electrons, the *A/D converter* and other sensor circuitry elements are not all manufactured perfectly equal to each other. In other words the "M" term in our model, is not exactly the same value for each photosite. Instead, "M" is an attribute of each photosite. This condition is called **Pixel Response Non-Uniformity** (PRNU).

Considering this, we will replace the factor "M" with " M_p ": we will use the subscript "p" as indication that "M" varies for each photosite on each given sensor position "p".

$$ADU_p = \mathbf{M}_p \cdot EL + RNS - \mu_{RNS} \quad \text{Eq. 3.13}$$

We must notice the sensitivity variations of " M_p " are not intended, they are *random* changes from photosite to photosite. In this sense, " M_p " is a random variable with respect to the surface of the sensor. This fact is represented in the notation with the use of bold typeface for " M_p ". However, we will consider that each photosite, along the time, has always its same " M_p " value: it only changes with ISO speed.

The average value (statistically speaking, the *expected value*) of all the " M_p " factors, corresponding to the photosites in the sensor surface, is probably what the manufacturing processing was aiming for. We will call "EM" (for **Expected Multiplier**) to this average:

$$EM = Eva(\mathbf{M}_p) \quad \text{Eq. 3.14}$$

Now we will model " M_p " as variations around this average. To this effect, we will consider " M_p " as composed by two additive components: one is the average "EM" and the other is the photosite sensitivity deviation with respect to that average. We will call " MD_p " to this latter component (for "**M**" **D**evelopment):

$$\mathbf{M}_p = EM + \mathbf{MD}_p \quad \text{Eq. 3.15}$$

Notice that this way to express " M_p " implies that the *expected value* of " MD_p " is zero. We can probe this applying the *expected value* operator to both ends of the previous equation and using Eq. 3.14:

$$\mathbf{M}_p = EM + \mathbf{MD}_p$$

$$Eva(\mathbf{M}_p) = Eva(EM + \mathbf{MD}_p)$$

$$Eva(\mathbf{M}_p) = Eva(EM) + Eva(\mathbf{MD}_p)$$

$$EM = EM + Eva(\mathbf{MD}_p)$$

$$\therefore Eva(\mathbf{MD}_p) = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 3.16}$$

We can now update our model using the above definition of " M_p " to get:

$$\mathbf{ADU}_p = (EM + \mathbf{MD}_p) \cdot \mathbf{EL} + \mathbf{RNS} - \mu_{RNS} \quad \text{Eq. 3.17}$$

The three sources of noise, represented with bold typeface in the above equation, are independent of each other. This will allow us to use simpler formulas to get the *expected value* and the *variance* of the resulting ADU.

Applying the *expected value* operator to both ends of our model equation Eq. 3.17; we get the (spatial) expected ADU value.

$$Eva(\mathbf{ADU}_p) = EM \cdot \lambda \quad \text{Eq. 3.18}$$

We can get the (spatial) *variance* of the photosite readings—in our model—considering the three random variables are independent among them. As a matter of notation, we will refer to the *variance* of the photosite sensitivities “ $Var(\mathbf{MD}_p)$ ” as “ $PRNU^2$ ”. Applying the *variance* operator to both ends of our model equation Eq. 3.17; we get:

$$Var(\mathbf{ADU}_p) = PRNU^2 \cdot \lambda^2 + (EM^2 + PRNU^2) \cdot \lambda + RN^2 \quad \text{Eq. 3.19}$$

This is the equation we were looking for from the very beginning. A simple equation aroused from the sensor model explaining the noise mathematical profile. There we can see how the three noise sources are additive components of the image variance, where the *PRNU noise* ($PRNU^2 \cdot \lambda^2$) grows quadratically with the signal (λ), the *photon shot noise* ($EM^2 \cdot \lambda$) grows linearly with the signal, and the read noise is a constant present even when there is no signal ($\lambda=0$).

Notice how the *variance* is a quadratic polynomial of λ , which represents the *expected* count of electrons in the photosites from the signal. The quadratic term is the synergy between the *PRNU noise* and the *photon shot noise*. Besides of the quadratic term, the PRNU also has impact in the linear λ term, all of this tells us the variance of sensitivities among the photosites (PRNU) is potentially a very strong source of noise.

Finally, we can express the SNR from the photosite ADU readings as in the following equation Eq. 3.20.

$$SNR = \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{PRNU}{EM}\right)^2 \cdot \lambda^2 + \left(\left(\frac{PRNU}{EM}\right)^2 + 1\right) \cdot \lambda + \left(\frac{RN}{EM}\right)^2}} \quad \text{Eq. 3.20}$$

Notice how the EM, which is the average conversion rate from electrons to ADU, scales up the *read noise* and the *PRNU noise*. The independent term λ inside the square root in the denominator corresponds to the *photon shot noise* component of the total noise.

3.3.1 The PRNU SNR Limit

If in the SNR equation (Eq. 3.20) we take the limit when the signal grows indefinitely, we will find the SNR is limited by the PRNU.

$$\lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} SNR = \frac{EM}{PRNU} \quad \text{Eq. 3.21}$$

This tells that the best SNR we can get from a camera can have a top limit imposed by the PRNU. Fortunately, for most DSLR camera sensors, the PRNU noise starts kicking close to the top limit of λ (e.g. 16,383 ADU for 14-bit raw files) and do not cause too much damage to the SNR just because the λ range ends before.

3.3.2 The Three Noise phases in the SNR

In the following graph we have a simulated SNR curve, where we can distinguish three phases showing the dominance of each noise type we have studied. At the left end of the curve, with low ADU values—in the area shown with orange background—the *read noise* makes the SNR somewhat below to the gray dotted line representing the ideal sensor, with only *photon shot noise*. In the second part, shown with green background, the SNR is dominated by the *photon shot noise* and "stays" with a slope around $\frac{1}{2}$. At the right end—in the area shown with pink background—the SNR slows down its growing rate and starts to bend over, to stay asymptotically below the PRNU limit (see Eq. 3.21), shown with a dotted red line.

Figure 5. SNR phases: orange: read noise, green: photon shot noise, red: PRNU noise

4 Example of Model Application

We have developed some formulas modeling the image raw pixel value and image noise from a digital camera CMOS sensor (Eq. 3.17 to 3.20). However, those formulas are expressed as functions of lambda " λ ", which is the *expected value* and the *variance* of the electron count in the sensor photosites. At first glance that might seem like an obstacle to use them to describe a concrete particular camera, but it is not. In this section we will show an example applying the model to "real" data.

For the sake of a simpler description, we will refer as *meanAdu* and *varAdu* to the left side of equations 3.18 and 3.19:

$$meanAdu = EM \cdot \lambda \tag{Eq. 4.1}$$

$$varAdu = PRNU^2 \cdot \lambda^2 + (EM^2 + PRNU^2) \cdot \lambda + RN^2 \tag{Eq. 4.2}$$

Let's suppose we make a regression with the noise variance *varAdu* as response variable with the *mean* pixel value and *mean*² as predictors. We will get an equation with the form:

$$var = u_2 \cdot mean^2 + u_1 \cdot mean + u_0 \quad \text{Eq. 4.3}$$

It is easy to probe [Dela15] that if the correlated *mean* pixel value is described by the Eq. 4.1 and *var* by Eq. 4.2, then:

$$u_2 = \frac{PRNU^2}{EM} \quad \text{Eq. 4.4}$$

$$u_1 = EM + \frac{PRNU^2}{EM} \quad \text{Eq. 4.5}$$

$$u_0 = RN^2 \quad \text{Eq. 4.6}$$

These equations can be solved to get camera characteristics:

$$RN = \sqrt{u_0} \quad \text{Eq. 4.7}$$

$$EM = u_1 - u_2 \quad \text{Eq. 4.8}$$

$$PRNU = \sqrt{(u_1 - u_2) \cdot u_2} \quad \text{Eq. 4.9}$$

However, the regression Eq. 4.3 is not easy to find with good accuracy, because those variables are related in a heteroscedastic way:

Figure 6. Noise variance versus mean pixel value from samples from photographs of a neutral color surface.

A good approximation regression to the relationship Eq. 4.3 is found in [Dela16] for the *Nikon D7000* at ISO speed 100, where:

$$u_2 = 7.972 \times 10^{-6}$$

$$u_1 = 0.4162$$

$$u_0 = 1.67$$

When we plug these values in Eq. 4.7 to 4.9, we obtain:

$$RN = 1.29 [ADU]$$

$$EM = 0.4162 \left[\frac{ADU}{e^-} \right]$$

$$PRNU = 0.44\% \cdot EM$$

5 Conclusions

We have seen how the Eq. 3.19, integrating the main components of a digital image noise, naturally arises from well-known characteristics of digital CMOS sensors. It is not necessary to sum those variances using as justification neither “the law of error propagation” nor with other totally generic reasons, when it can be better understood in the way proposed here.

6 References

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